

Potentiometric Tb^{3+} -PVC membrane sensor based on 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(2-oxo-1,2-diphenylethylidene)naphthalene-2-carbohydrazide as an ion carrier

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Abstract : A new Tb^{3+} -PVC membrane sensor was constructed using a suitable ion carrier named 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(2-oxo-1,2-diphenylethylidene)naphthalene-2-carbohydrazide (HNC). It has a linear dynamic range between 5.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2} M, with a near Nernstian slope of 19.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade, a detection limit of 4.0×10^{-7} M. The effects of the membrane composition, pH, and additive anionic influence on the response properties were investigated. The best performance was obtained with a membrane composition of 30% poly(vinyl chloride), 66% solvent mediator (NB), 2% sodium tetraphenyl borate and 2% HNC. The potentiometric response of the sensor is independent of pH of the solution in the pH range 2.5–8.6. The proposed sensor has a very low response time (<10 s). The developed sensor was successfully applied as an indicator electrode in the Tb^{III} ion potentiometric titration with EDTA and in the determination of F^- in mouth wash samples.

Keywords : PVC membrane, potentiometry, sensor, ion-selective electrode.

Introduction

Terbium is one of the members of lanthanide series that can be found in houses and equipments such as color televisions, fluorescent lamps, energy-saving lamps, glasses, gasoline-cracking catalysts and movie projectors¹. The main methods for low level determination of rare earth ions in a solution includes are spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS) and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES)²⁻⁴. These methods are time consuming, involving sample preparations, and too expensive for most analytical laboratories. The sample was destroyed after measurement. Potentiometric sensors have shown to be very effective tools for analysis of a wide variety of cations, anions, and molecules. Construction and application of ion selective electrode as a potentiometric sensor offers interesting advantages such as simplicity, speed, relatively fast response, low cost, wide linear dynamic range and ease of preparation and procedures⁵. Our research team have recently introduced PVC based membrane sensors for different cations based on different neutral ionophores⁶⁻¹⁹. Among these metal ions, limited attention has been paid to the development of lanthanide

electrodes. There are only some reports in the literature concerning the design of highly selective ionophores for terbium²⁰⁻²². In this work, we report a highly selective terbium electrode using 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(2-oxo-1,2-diphenylethylidene)naphthalene-2-carbohydrazide (HNC) (Fig. 1) as a good ionophore in poly vinyl chloride matrix for the fabrication of Tb^{3+} -PVC membrane electrode.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of HNC.

Experimental

Reagents :

The Merck Co. was the provider for the reagent grades of acetophenon (AP), benzyl acetate (BA), dibutyl phthalate (DBP), nitrobenzene (NB), tetrahydrofuran (THF),

sodium tetraphenylborate (NaTPB), and high relative molecular weight PVC. Nitrate and chloride salts of all cations were purchased from Merck Chemical and Aldrich Co. During the experiments, doubly distilled deionized water was used.

Preparation of the electrode :

The PVC membranes were prepared according to the following general procedure. The required ingredients for the membrane construction (30 mg PVC, 66 mg NB, 2 mg NaTPB and 2 mg ionophore) were mixed and dissolved in 3 mL of dry THF. The resulting clear mixture was evaporated slowly until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (3–5 mm i.d.) was dipped into the mixture for about 5 s so that a nontransparent membrane of about 0.3 mm thickness is formed^{23–33}. The tube was then pulled out from the mixture and kept at room temperature for about 12 h. The tube was then filled with internal filling solution (1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ of TbCl₃). The electrode was finally conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a 1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ terbium chloride. A silver/silver chloride electrode was used as an internal reference electrode.

The EMF measurements :

The equipment for the EMF (electromotive force) measurements consisted of; (a) Ag–AgCl | internal solution, 1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ TbCl₃ | PVC membrane | sample solution | Hg–Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (satd.) and (b) a Corning ion analyzer with a 250 pH/mV meter for the potential measurements at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. The EMF observations were made relative to a double-junction saturated

calomel electrode (SCE, Philips) with its chamber filled with an ammonium nitrate solution. The activities were calculated according to the Debye-Huckel procedure³⁴.

Results and discussion

The potential response of the Tb³⁺ electrode :

In order to check the HNC suitability as an ionophore for different metal ions, HNC was used as an active ion carrier to design numerous PVC membrane ISEs under identical conditions for a great variety of metal ions, including alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. Only the Tb³⁺ ions displayed a stronger response (with a slope of 19.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade) to the HNC developed sensor in comparison with that of the other tested cations. Except for Tb³⁺ ion, the slope of the corresponding potential pM^{n+} plots is much lower than the expected Nernstian slopes of 59, 29.5 and 20 mV decade⁻¹ for the univalent, bivalent and trivalent cations, respectively.

The influence of membrane composition :

It is reported that the membrane composition and, especially in some cases, the nature of the additive have a significant influence on the sensitivity and selectivity for a certain ionophore^{35–39}. Thus, different aspects of preparation of membranes based on HNC were optimized and the results are given in Table 1. It can be seen that the ionophore amount increases up to a 2% value in the presence of 2% of NaTPB and 66% of polar solvent (NB) results in the best sensitivity. Generally, the presence of lipophilic anions in a cation-selective membrane based on a neutral carrier not only diminishes the ohmic resistance

Table 1. Optimization of the membrane ingredients

Sensor no.	Composition of the membrane (w/w%)				Slope (mV decade ⁻¹)	Dynamic linear range (M)
	PVC	Plasticizer	HNC	NaTPB		
1	30	NB, 68	2	0	12.5 ± 0.4	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-2}
2	30	NB, 67	2	1	16.4 ± 0.2	1.0×10^{-6} – 5.0×10^{-2}
3	30	NB, 65	2	3	17.7 ± 0.5	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
4	30	NB, 67	1	2	17.3 ± 0.3	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
5	30	NB, 65	3	2	18.5 ± 0.2	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
6	30	NB, 66	2	2	19.8 ± 0.4	5.0×10^{-7} – 1.0×10^{-2}
7	30	DBP, 66	2	2	16.9 ± 0.5	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-2}
8	30	AP, 66	2	2	18.2 ± 0.3	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
9	30	BA, 66	2	2	17.4 ± 0.6	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-2}

and enhances the response behavior and selectivity but also, in cases where the extraction capability is poor, it increases the membrane electrode sensitivity⁴⁰⁻⁴³. Since NB is a plasticizer with high dielectric constant, it helps to better extraction of polar ion Tb^{III} with high hydration energy from aqueous solution to organic layer of the membrane. As a result, membrane composition (no. 6) of 30% PVC, 2% HNC, 2% NaTPB and 66% NB exhibited a better Nernstian potential response with faster response time and a better linearity in linear response range.

Calibration graph :

The optimum equilibration time for the proposed sensor in the presence of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ $TbCl_3$ was 12 h, after which it would generate stable potentials in contact with terbium solutions. The best sensor composition showed a linear response toward the activity of Tb^{III} ions in the range of 5.0×10^{-7} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ (Fig. 2), with a slope of $19.8 \pm 0.4 mV$ decade⁻¹. The lower limit of detection, determined by extrapolating two segments of the calibration graph, was estimated to be $4 \times 10^{-8} M$.

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of the terbium electrode based on HNC. The results are based on five replicate measurements.

pH effect :

In order to study the pH effect on the sensor performance, the potentials were determined at pH values from 2.0 to 11.0 (concentrated NaOH or HCl was used for pH adjustment) at a specific Tb^{3+} concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and as found the potential to be fairly constant in the pH range of 2.8-9.0 (Fig. 3). The observed drift at higher pH may be attributed to the formation of some Tb^{3+}

Fig. 3. The pH effect of the test solution on the potential response of the terbium sensor (no. 6).

hydroxyl complexes in the solution. At lower pH, the potentials increased, indicating that the membrane sensor responded to protonium ions, as a result of some extent nitrogen atom protonation of the ionophore.

Dynamic response time of Tb^{3+} sensor :

In this study, the practical response time was recorded by changing the Tb^{3+} concentration in solution in a concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} mol L^{-1}$. The results are shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen, in the whole concentration range the electrode reached its equilibrium response in a very short time (<10 s). This is most probably due to the fast exchange kinetics of the complexation-decomplexation of Tb^{3+} ions with the ionophore at the test solution-membrane interface.

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the terbium electrode (no. 6) for step changes in the Tb^{3+} concentration : (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, (C) $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, (D) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, (E) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Electrode selectivity :

Selectivity is perhaps the single electrode characteristic, that defines the nature of the device and the extent to which it may be employed in the determination of a particular ion in the presence of other interfering ions. For the selectivity assessment of the praseodymium membrane electrodes, their corresponding potentiometric selectivity coefficients were evaluated by the matched potential method (MPM)⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. According to the MPM, a specified activity (concentration) of primary ions (A) is added to a reference solution and the potential is measured. In a separate experiment, interfering ions (B) are successively added to an identical reference solution, until the measured potential matches the one obtained before by adding primary ions. The MPM selectivity coefficient, K^{MPM} is then given by the resulting primary ion to interfering ion activity (concentration) ratio, $K^{\text{MPM}} = \Delta a_A/a_B$. Table 2

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients of the developed Tb³⁺ electrode

Ion	K^{MPM}
Sm ³⁺	5.4×10^{-4}
Gd ³⁺	2.3×10^{-3}
Yb ³⁺	6.5×10^{-4}
Pr ³⁺	5.8×10^{-4}
Eu ³⁺	1.0×10^{-4}
Lu ³⁺	7.9×10^{-4}
Cr ³⁺	3.7×10^{-3}
Fe ³⁺	4.2×10^{-3}
Ca ²⁺	1.0×10^{-3}
Mg ²⁺	7.3×10^{-4}
Na ⁺	5.7×10^{-4}
K ⁺	8.2×10^{-4}
Co ²⁺	8.6×10^{-4}
Cd ²⁺	2.7×10^{-3}
Ni ²⁺	1.0×10^{-3}
Cu ²⁺	4.5×10^{-3}
Pb ²⁺	5.8×10^{-4}

presents the potentiometric selectivity coefficients of the HNC-based terbium selective electrode. The selectivity data indicate that for all diverse cations used, the K^{MPM} values are in the order of 4.5×10^{-3} or smaller, indicating they would not significantly disturb the functioning of the Tb³⁺ electrode. Therefore, the electrode can be used for the determination of Tb^{III} ions in the presence of certain interfering ions.

Furthermore, the characteristics of the sensor were compared with those of the best terbium electrodes reported in the literature (Table 3)²⁶⁻²⁸. These results make it evident that the developed sensor is superior to the formerly reported Tb^{III} sensors in terms of selectivity, detection limit and dynamic concentration range.

Analytical application :

The developed Tb³⁺ membrane sensor was found to work well under laboratory conditions. It was successfully applied to the titration of 1.0×10^{-4} M Tb³⁺ solution with a standard 1.0×10^{-2} M EDTA, and the resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 5. As seen, the amount of Tb³⁺ in solution can be accurately determined with the electrode.

This sensor was also successfully applied to the determination of F⁻ ions in two mouth wash samples. 1.0 g of each sample was taken and diluted with distilled water in a 100 ml flask and titrated with a Tb³⁺ solution (1.0×10^{-3} M). The results, after triplicate measurements, are summarized in Table 4. There was a satisfactory agreement among the declared fluoride contents, the values determined by the sensor.

Conclusion :

According to the results obtained in this paper, 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(2-oxo-1,2-diphenylethylidene)naphthalene-2-carbohydrazide (HNC) could be considered as an neutral

Table 3. Comparison of different Tb³⁺ electrodes

Parameter	Ref. 20	Ref. 21	Ref. 22	This work
LR (mol L ⁻¹)	1.0×10^{-6} - 1.0×10^{-1}	1.0×10^{-6} - 1.0×10^{-1}	1.0×10^{-5} - 1.0×10^{-1}	5.0×10^{-7} - 1.0×10^{-2}
DL (mol L ⁻¹)	8.0×10^{-7}	8.6×10^{-7}	7.0×10^{-6}	4.0×10^{-7}
Response time (s)	~ 10	15	<20	<10
pH range	3.5-8.0	3.8-8.2	3.5-7.7	2.8-9.0
Slope (mV decade ⁻¹)	19.7	19.4	19.8	19.8
log $K_{\text{sel}} > -2$	Gd	Gd	Ce, La, Dy, Yb, Sm	-

Fig. 5. Potentiometric titration curve of 20.0 mL from a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M Tb^{3+}$ solution with $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ of EDTA.

Table 4. Fluoride ions determination in mouth wash solutions

Sample	Labeled (ppm)	Found ISE ^a (ppm)
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Aquafresh, Brentford, UK)	1350	1377 ± 21
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Eurodont, DuroDont GmbH)	1450	1483 ± 18

^aSuggested Tb^{3+} sensor.

ion carrier for creation of a PVC-based membrane for the determination of Tb^{III} ion in solution. The results showed that the membrane with NB plasticizer having composition 30 : 2 : 66 : 2 (PVC : NaTPB : NB : HNC) performs best. The recommended sensor displayed a quick response time of <10 s and its potential responses were pH independent across the range of 2.5–8.6. The proposed electrode reveals excellent selectivity for Tb^{3+} over a wide variety of alkali, alkaline earth, some transitions and heavy metal ions. This electrode could be also successfully applied to the determination of F^- ion in mouth wash solution.

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